

VIRTUAL EDUCATION, A CHALLENGE FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF THE ROMANIAN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

Purpose – The authors tried to analyze eLearning, because the 2020 pandemic crisis showed an old weakness of the Romanian education system. The analysis was seen as a social phenomenon in the entire Romanian education system, in which the need for eLearning became evident after March 15, 2020, the date that affected many elements of society, including education.

Methodology/approach - 19 questions, through an electronic questionnaire, to which 200 respondents answered, formed the basis of the research methodology and was applied to a group of 200 respondents between April 29, 2020 at 1 pm and April 30, 2020 at 1 pm. It is specified that the respondents are students at the University of Petroșani for undergraduate and master's studies in the academic year 2019-2020.

Findings – The lack of an eLearning platform led to the sending of courses to students by email in pdf format. The lack of teacher training was limited to 50% of the effective percentage of online courses and only to 30% in videoconferencing. The students being more adaptable participated in a higher proportion in the courses from March to May 2020, counting 87%. It should be noted that 42% used the phone for this activity.

Research limitations/implications – Even if the respondents, as mentioned, are only from the University of Petroșani, the study can be extrapolated to provide an image for the Romanian education system.

Practical implications – The demonstration of the representativeness of the University of Petroșani in relation to a national education system for the implementation of eLearning in crisis situations leads to the important conclusion of this short research. This conclusion says that Covid19 has changed education in Romania, and classical education is likely to undergo significant changes because of these three months of exclusive online education.

Originality/value – Romania did in two months what it has not done in years, so at the beginning of May, most schools and universities migrated to an online education system.

Key words: eLearning, teaching process, digital tools, education platform, virtual classroom

1. eLearning in Romanian Education System

1.1. An Overview of the Educational Platforms in the Romanian Education System

The analysis of the stage of implementation of eLearning in the primary and secondary education system in Romania was a necessity for evaluating the impact of eLearning for Romanian education during COVID-19. In Romania, the eLearning software market has been dominated since 2000 by the company SIVECO, which developed the AeL solution. This solution has been implemented in the primary and pre-university system. There are implementations of this solution in other fields as well, including at the University of Petroșani through the implementation in the period 2010-2013 of a European project PODSDRU 59676, focused on eLearning in partnership with SIVECO Romania SA. In recent years, Ascedia SA has appeared on the Romanian eLearning market, providing the LMS LIVRESQ solution, delivered together with the use of free licenses for education offered by Google and Microsoft (G Suite and Microsoft 365 A1). The Ascedia solution is aimed at the pre-university environment. It should be

noted that both companies have formed a partnership with the Romanian Ministry of Education and Research (MER).

The analysis cannot be limited to the pre-university system. For example, the history of eLearning in the university system begin with Spiru Haret University (SHU), that has used a Learning Management System (LMS) platform called Blackboard Learn for teaching, collaborative work, testing and student management since 2006. This platform has increased the number of SHU students 10 times in 4 years, starting with 2004.

In the years since the appearance of distance learning (DL) in Romania, in 1995, 58% of universities stated to use eLearning solutions. Currently, all Romanian universities use eLearning platforms, the most popular being Moodle. There are also platforms from Google and Microsoft.

Because the study analyzes the University of Petroșani, the authors analyzed the evolution of eLearning at this university. The University of Petroșani started in 1998 the first study programs focused on a DL structure. In 2011, a LMS (Learning Management System) eLearning platform called CourseMill was implemented. (Lupu, Edelhauser, Ionica, 2010), (CourseMill, 2020) Currently there is a small eLearning platform based on Moodle, insufficiently customized, without virtual classes, without content, without test modules, which places the University of Petroșani at the bottom of the ranking of Romanian universities in terms of virtual education. This situation is abnormal because at UPET there has been a collaborative educational platform from Microsoft-Office 365 A1 since 2013. (Edelhauser, Ionica, Lupu, 2010 b).

Overall, the technical or administrative details, the main topic was the ability of eLearning to replace classical education or their combination. Everything starts from meeting the quality criteria from a pedagogical, academic, administrative and technical point of view. Research to date reveals eLearning capabilities if it has a proper design. Criteria to be met, with decisive value in an eLearning system are the quality criteria to which each element is equally important - Institutional support, Teaching and learning, Course development, Support for faculty members, Course structure and Evaluation.

Google and Microsoft have developed digital education platforms. Google's G Suite for Education contains tools that integrate new technologies into teaching and improve teaching, learning, and collaboration in schools (Figure 1). Microsoft for Education offers similar tools so that each student can achieve better learning outcomes. Teachers receive tools for organizing virtual classes, by planning lessons, until maintaining a constant connection with colleagues (Figure 2). In Romania, any educational institution can activate for free the free version of G Suite for Education and Microsoft 365 A1. (Edu365, 2020)

Îmbunătățește predarea, învățarea și colaborarea în școala ta

Figure 1. School 365 Platform for Education G-Suite for Education

Caracteristicile platformei Școala365

Principalele caracteristici ale platformei Școala365 sunt instrumentele inovatoare necesare pentru gestionarea fiecărei instituții de învățământ. Acestea facilitează sistemul de management al școlii, catalogul electronic, predarea, învățarea, comunicarea profesor-elev-părinte și multe altele.

Catalog Electronic

Catalogul școlar electronic asigură comunicarea directă părinți - profesori - elevi, trimite notificări în timp real despre note, absențe, ședințe, teme.

School Management

Cu sistemul de School Management (Secretariat365), administrația școlii are o imagine de 360° a activității școlare.

Integrări365

Platforma Școala365 are potențialul de a transforma clasa tradițională într-o experiență unică și inovatoare de învățare pentru toți elevii.

Social365

Este un instrument digital de comunicare, conceput și dezvoltat special pentru școli.

Figure 2. School 365 Platform for Education Microsoft for Education

The strategy of a mix of platforms was the path followed by Romanian universities, to be able to support distance learning or part-time learning. The University of Oradea and the Transilvania University of Brașov use Moodle. Politehnica Timișoara has its own version of a virtual campus. The Technical University of Cluj Napoca and Politehnica București use the Microsoft Microsoft 365 A1 platform. Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu and the University of Craiova use Google G Suite. Gheorghe Asachi University of Iasi uses Microsoft Microsoft 365 A1 and Google G Suite.

1.2. Designing an eLearning Platform at the University of Petroșani, using Microsoft 365 A1 Licence

The success of an educational process is offered by the collaborative work and the continuous communication, fact accomplished by the complete use of the resources of the Microsoft 365 platform. This platform allows the centering on the student needs, as it happens in the traditional education (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The structure of a virtual class in OneNote Class Notebook.

The authors' experience in using the platform, allows the exemplification of the way of working in mixed regime. In the classroom, students access their resources, assigned to their own account, in order to be able to present their work. (Edelhauser, Lupu, 2012), (Edelhauser, Ionica, Lupu, 2010 a)

Also, in class, students load all their activity individually, in the specified sections, thus giving the student the opportunity to continue their study at home. This method also provides information security and compliance. (Edelhauser, Ionica, Lupu, 2010 b)

2. eLearning during the COVID-19 Pandemic at the University of Petroșani

2.1. Methodology

"Is Romania ready for eLearning in the period of the coronavirus pandemic 2019-2020?" is the question around which the study carried out at the University of Petroșani revolved. To collect the information, the authors used an online questionnaire, with 19 questions, the respondents being students of the University of Petroșani, of the academic year 2019-2020.

2.2. Respondents

The questionnaire was completed by over 200 students from the University of Petroșani, and the data were collected for 24 hours, starting with April 29, 2020 at 1 p.m. the data collected allowed the authors to ascertain the existence of trends in online education. The analysis of these tendencies allows the proposal of useful measures for decision makers in the university or in the education system.

2.3. Findings and discussions. Graphical results

There have been opinions that the pandemic has increased the level of importance of eLearning. This explains question Q1 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Q1, "In what year did you first use an eLearning platform or did you go through an education-focused video conferencing session?"

The answers provided show the great ability of students to adapt, so they quickly migrated to online courses (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Q2, “Did you attend online courses between 16th March 2020 and 30th April 2020?”

Because the way students perceive eLearning is diverse (for some students WhatsApp is an eLearning platform), it is difficult to assess their level of involvement in online courses. The answers to questions Q11, Q12 and Q13 show that 86% is too high compared to reality.

Figure 6. Q3, “What hardware equipment did you use to attend the online courses? Answer by choosing the degree of use for each option (number of students).”

Table 1. Student attendance for classic or online classes by hours per day

Hours of Courses/Day	Online	Classic
0	9	16
1	54	34
2	83	39
3	22	18
4	23	25
5	5	12
6	8	44
More Than 6	5	21

Analyzing the collected data, we can see an increase in the number of students in online courses for those who participate up to 2 hours a day. These students are the ones who participate in 5 or 6 hours in the classical system, and the courses were probably not taken. The authors appreciate that the presence is lower and the dropout rate is higher in eLearning classes (Table 1).

The analysis shows a lower average number of hours online, 2.43, compared to the classic, 3.70. The graph in the figure shows that the high density is for 2 hours a day, while in the classic it is 6 hours a day (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Q6, “What was the number of hours per day dedicated to your online courses during the state of emergency?”, and Q7, “What was the number of hours per day dedicated to conducting the courses in the classic format by you in the period prior to the declaration of the state of emergency?”.

Figure 8. Q8, “What online communication system did you mainly use to communicate with the teacher? Answer by choosing the degree of use for each option (number of students).”

The lack of implementation of an eLearning system is proved by the collected data. 119 students stated that email is the main communication. The second option is a social networking platform, Facebook (Figure 8).

Figure 9. Q11, “Were the virtual classes used for the seminar or project classes? If so, specify which.”

The virtual classroom is the tool that allows eLearning a good development of activities. 30% of the students stated that they used a virtual class Google or Microsoft (Figure 9), which contradicts the rest of the information collected by the authors from the Dean's Office of two faculties of the three, which indicates a degree of use of only 14% of virtual classes.

Figure 10. Q12, “Were predefined online tests used for online testing? If so, specify which.”

Another important aspect of the second semester was the use of online tests. 48% of students stated that they used the online tests between April and May 2020 (Figure 10). The data was confirmed by new information collected from the Faculty of Science and the Faculty of Mining, which showed levels of 43% and 48% for the use of online tests.

Figure 11. Q13, “What program did you use during the video conferencing courses?”.

Because the video interaction had an important component, this aspect was also investigated. The data showed that during the COVID-19 crisis no specialized platforms were used, the favorite tool being Zoom, which is free and easy (Figure 11).

Figure 12. Q14, “Out of the total of 5–7 study disciplines allocated to the 2nd semester of the academic year 2019–2020, for how many of them did you use online courses?”

The proof that the university did not have a preoccupation for the training of teachers for working online is provided by the percentage of 50% of the courses that take place online. It is concluded that three out of seven teachers (1, 2 and 3 - blue, orange and gray) used the online course effectively, and the students participated in 3.45 out of seven courses (Q14) (Figure 12).

3. Discussion and conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic has made eLearning a necessity. This statement refers to the whole world, including Romania. The migration from classic to eLearning has been easy for strong universities. The same challenges were faced by all levels of education. The actual study of authors went to small schools and universities, because they had a level of similarity offered by the fact that they used very little eLearning.

Another important aspect of the choice of authors was the importance of small universities, which are relevant at regional level. They have a supporting role in education in less developed areas. This explains the relevance of the University of Petrosani, considered by the authors to be representative for the three-month period in which all education was online.

According to the authors, immediately after Romania declared, on March 15, 2020, the state of emergency, conducting such a study became unavoidable. The importance of this major change in the education system has been identified by the authors, who have almost 10 years of experience in the field of eLearning. The experience in the field of authors' management is not to be ignored. The lack of preparation for such a change in small universities is also a reality at the University of Petrosani.

Using the Microsoft 365 A1 platform, the authors developed their own tools for online education in the first 45 days of the state of emergency. This fact was presented in Chapter 1 of this work. Other teachers, due to a low level of training in eLearning, have adapted with difficulty.

The lack of adaptation to the new conditions made the authors take an extra step in the second part of the state of emergency. They tried to provide advice to other teachers and started a questionnaire-based investigation, benefiting from the involvement of a very large number of students. These students were involved by authors in online courses and projects, as well as webinars. An explanation of the good data collection from students in such a short period of time is provided by the fact that in the period 2016-2020, Eduard Edelhauser was the vice-rector of the university for student issues and, in February 2020, he was the candidate to the position of rector at the University of Petroșani, being one of the most important figures for the students from the academic community from Petroșani.

Using the data collected in this study, the authors with good expertise in the field, identified a few relevant results:

- The high degree of student participation in online courses, 87% between March and May 2020 shows the adaptability of students to virtual education;
- A communication tool, email, was used as a testing tool in a proportion of 33-40%;
- Another communication tool, WhatsApp, was used as a testing tool in a proportion of 6 to 12%;
- The percentage of online testing varied between 45% and 52%;
- 42% of students participated in online courses using a smartphone, which became the most used equipment;
- The number of online courses was only 50%;
- The number of courses held online with video conferencing was only 30%.

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